

Good Manners and Right Conduct: Post-pandemic Challenges of Junior High School Teachers in Digos City Division

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Abstract. This study explored the challenges faced by junior high school teachers in the Digos City Division in implementing good manners and right conduct (GMRC) post-pandemic. Ten (10) teachers applied intervention to address the misbehavior of learners in school. This study used a phenomenological approach to extract the participants' ideas. The virtual in-depth interview was employed to gather information regarding their respective narratives as they imposed good manners and right conduct in the classroom. The thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study revealed the experiences of junior high school teachers as they addressed misbehavior, which affects the teaching and learning process, and delved into evident disruptive behavior, undesired behavior, and declining learner's interest. Teachers usually reported that these disturbing behaviors in the classroom were intolerable and stress-provoking, and they had to spend a great deal of time and energy managing the classroom. However, the teachers employed coping mechanisms: reacting appropriately to misbehavior, applying preventive methods, and extensive classroom management. The study's findings highlight the importance of effective classroom management, professional understanding of learners' behavior, and disciplinary strategies for misbehavior.

KEY WORDS

1. good manners and right conduct
2. Post-pandemic challenges
3. Junior High School

Date Received: May 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: June 01, 2024 — Date Published: July 5, 2024

1. Introduction

Learners are at the heart of teaching and learning. Students would learn effectively if they are willing to learn. However, students may conduct disruptive behavior in the classroom. The impact of learners' bad manners and negative behavior conduct is dangerous. A single learner's bad manners can influence his own and other learners' learning. Similarly, an affected student can cause other students to become anxious and insecure in the classroom. Learners' bad manners can spread throughout the learning environment and influence other students. As a result, teachers find difficulty in managing their classrooms. This presents a unique challenge for teachers. While traditionally focused on curriculum delivery, they may now need to dedicate additional time and effort to fostering a respectful and responsible classroom environment. This could involve explicitly teaching social skills, creating opportunities for positive student interaction, and modeling appropriate behavior themselves. The lack of

clear boundaries between physical and virtual spaces further complicates the issue, requiring teachers to establish new expectations for online etiquette and respectful communication. Findings of a study by Read (2020) indicate that 78 percent of students in North American higher education did not feel online experiences engaging, and 75 percent of them preferred face-to-face interactions with instructors and peers. However, according to Raes et al. (2019), the majority of students have attended the class due to the flexibility of a blended or hybrid- learning environment, though some took leave either because they were sick or needed to perform home tasks. This global change has had a great impact, particularly on ethics and manners. There is a decline in morals among students in this new generation. This is because the environment in which they are living today sometimes does not support the formation of their morals, and they are prone to foreign cultures being influenced. The prevailing issue that has been identified by researchers is that besides adjusting themselves to the new normal environment, the advancement of technology has caused a decline in students' manners towards educators because educators only transfer knowledge to the students and they do not play role models and guide them for their future (Widianto, 2018). Due to this reason, it is believed that teaching should emphasize ethics and manners more because they are the most expected outcome of education (Pipin, 2022). According to Pham (2019), the level of school violence in Japan is growing to the point where students are taking their own lives as a response to the increasingly unsafe atmosphere. The Bullying Prevention Act was officially signed into law by the president in 2013. As a consequence of this, it is required of every school to devise a plan and an organizational framework to prevent bullying and to report occurrences of bullying. On the third Friday of every March, the country of Australia hosts an event that is held annually and is known

as "National Action Day Against Bullying and School Violence." Even in Finland, which is often regarded as having an education system that is the pinnacle of excellence anywhere in the world, students in schools are subjected to bullying. Kiva is a program that was designed by educators to counteract bullying and is currently being utilized in more than ninety percent of the country's educational institutions. According to Mr. Chris Henderson, who is the Deputy Director of the Institute of Vocational Training at the University of Waikato in New Zealand, student-on-student violence can also be found in New Zealand (Pham, 2019) In the Philippines, legislators saw the need to bring back Good Manners and Right Conduct as a school subject because of the rising criminality and moral values degradation in the streets and inside our homes committed by youngsters. It was also observed that there was a downgrading of values education in the curriculum when we implemented the K-12 program in 2013. Finding solutions to possible students' behavioral problems, which may negatively impact their education and relationships with others is a concern. Teachers believe that exploring students' behavioral issues is an indispensable enterprise as the longer they are left untreated, the worse they become. In ensuring smooth learning processes for students with behavioral problems, schools, play significant roles in setting and enforcing rules to instill conforming values in students. This is essential as undesirable actions such as aggression, disobedience, and destruction of properties cause disruptions at schools, and homes and may even impact the local community. In Digos City Division, particularly in the Secondary Schools District, Studying students' behavioral problems is vital to the teachers. Their roles in the teaching process are not limited to leading students' learning and providing them with information. Instead, as a process, it ensures the stability of students' behavior and their emotional, spiritual, cognitive, and social well-

being. More so, rampant cases of bullying and abuse were reported among junior high school learners. It is in this context that the researcher came up with this study. This study aims to identify practical applications of its results to benefit various stakeholders in education. The primary beneficiaries include the Department of Education, specifically the Digos City Division's Secondary Schools District officials. The findings can be used to develop new avenues for supporting teachers who deliver the good manners and right conduct (GMRC) curriculum. This support could come from technical assistance programs to enhance their teaching skills. Additionally, the study's insights can inform policy changes that strengthen and ensure the long-term effectiveness of the GMRC program within the educational system. As participants of this study, advise-teachers would benefit by reflecting on their thoughts and past experiences, particularly the challenges they faced in teaching good manners and proper conduct, which can serve as a baseline for their professional development plans. Learners would gain insights into how they develop good manners and proper conduct, preparing them for more significant responsibilities in life, learning to behave appropriately and react positively to various situations while also exploring the reasons behind some learners' bad manners and misbehavior

1.2. *Research Questions—*

- (1) What are the lived experiences of teachers in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of the teachers on the challenges they encountered in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences of the teachers in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners?

1.3. *Review of Significant Literature—*

1.3.1. *Classroom Management and Teacher Effectiveness—*Effective classroom management reduces disruptive behaviors and creates a conducive learning environment

in class. Future researchers are encouraged to consider other aspects of teenage misbehavior as they face challenges and opportunities not covered in this research, with future studies in different locations and communities providing a better comparison and deeper understanding of the phenomenon being explored.

Operational Definitions: The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Good manners and right conduct (GMRC) refer to universally accepted basic social values, etiquette, and proper behavior that convey respect to those with whom one interacts (RA 11476, 2019). In this study, GMRC refers to the methods teachers use to instill good behavior in learners while delivering quality education. Post-pandemic challenges refer to the changes that occurred during the health crisis, causing negative behavioral changes in learners. Specifically, this study pertains to the struggles junior high school teachers face in dealing with behavioral problems among learners in face-to-face classes.

1.1. *Purpose of the Study—*The purpose of this phenomenological study was to determine teachers' experiences in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners, their coping mechanisms, and their insights into understanding their behavior.

(George et al., 2018; Patrick, 2019). Techniques such as verbal instruction, instructional supervision, and delegation of authority (Good, 2019; Obot, 2018; Nima, 2019) are essential. However, strategies vary based on teaching

styles, qualifications, and class size (Walter, 2019). Positive management leads to increased engagement and academic performance (Gage et al., 2018; Roger, 2020).

1.3.2. Positive Peer Influence—Students can influence their peers positively by modeling respectful behavior, fostering a culture of good manners (Junge et al., 2020; Tuerk et al., 2021). Social competence develops through interactions with peers, parents, and teachers (Lecce et al., 2017; Pradesa et al., 2023). Effective parenting, supported by social networks, also plays a crucial role (Yang et al., 2020). Peer and teacher support significantly impact children’s mental well-being and social skills (Suresh et al., 2021; Wahyuni, 2023; Hellfeldt et al., 2020; Luna et al., 2020).

1.3.3. Disruptive Behavior—Disruptive behaviors range from minor infractions to serious incidents (The IRIS Center, 2021). Teachers often struggle with classroom management, leading to stress and reduced instructional time (Flower et al., 2019). Addressing these behaviors is critical for maintaining a positive learning environment (Stewart et al., 2018; Smith et al., 2019; Johnson, 2019). Understanding and proactively managing these behaviors can mitigate their negative impact (Mardliyah, 2019).

1.3.4. Dealing with Undesired Behavior—Teachers should set clear behavior standards and use positive reinforcement to manage disruptions (The IRIS Center, 2021; Puspitaloka Syafitri, 2019). Proactive strategies prevent minor issues from escalating (Aldrup et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2019). Effective training in classroom management is essential to reduce teacher stress and attrition (Stevenson et al., 2020). Understanding student behavior and backgrounds helps tailor management techniques (The IRIS Center, 2021).

1.3.5. Declining Learners’ Interest—There’s a concern about declining interest in science and technical fields (Kang et al., 2019; Cheung, 2018). Factors fostering interest in

these areas must be identified to develop effective interventions (Rathod, 2018). Creating a structured environment promotes engagement and limits disruptive behaviors (The IRIS Center, 2021).

1.3.6. Coping Mechanisms—Teachers should use positive feedback to address negative behaviors and maintain a productive classroom environment (Puspitaloka Syafitri, 2019; Mardliyah, 2019). Training in positive behavior management strategies is crucial for reducing teacher stress and turnover (The IRIS Center, 2021; Stevenson et al., 2020).

1.3.7. Preventive Methods—Adopting proactive coping strategies helps manage undesired behaviors (Aldrup et al., 2018). Teachers should understand student backgrounds and apply culturally sensitive management techniques (The IRIS Center, 2021).

1.4. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on the psychoanalytic theory of Sigmund Freud considered the origin of behavioral problems. According to McLeod (2019), a collection of psychological ideas and therapeutic techniques with roots in the research and theories of Sigmund Freud is referred to as psychoanalysis. Psychology is a discipline, meanwhile psychoanalysis is one technique within that discipline. Freud concluded that they were part of human psychology, which he called life instincts, a product of a force with which a person is born and directly attributable to the instinctive desire to destroy. Based on this view, he concluded that this intuitive destructive energy could be displayed as actions, games, or activities that conform to acceptable social values and mores or as undesirable behavior. Positive emotions are important psychological components that stimulate motivation, meta-cognition, and cognition, thereby positively influencing learning behavior (Efklides et al., 2018; Hascher Hagenauer, 2018; Pekrun, 2018). The behaviorist, B.F. Skinner based his theory of operant conditioning on the assumption that most behav-

ior is learned and acquired through the individual's environment. Generally, human behavior is divided into normal and abnormal behavior which may be linked to mental health (Tovarek et al., 2018). Most people display normal and acceptable behavioral patterns, which reflect their ability to effectively adapt to their social environment and conform to societal norms. An abnormal behavior, in contrast, signifies internal and social discord experienced by individuals in society. Some proponents of this perspective studied the effect of physiology on the adaptive behavior of individuals through the study of hormones present in the endocrine system, which have a significant and direct impact on the bloodstream. They also observed the effect of the pituitary gland as the link between testosterone and behavioral problems in several studies. Others focused their studies on neurotransmitters as catecholamine and cholinergic neurotransmitters have long been associated with behavioral issues. In contrast, serotonin and GABA aminobutyric acid deficiencies have been linked to hyper-stimulation and affect psychological functions (Yu et al., 2020). The study is guided by the Education Act of 1982 which provided that it is the policy of the state to establish and maintain a complete, adequate, and integrated system of education relevant to the goals of national development, one of which is to achieve and strengthen national unity and consciousness and preserve, develop and promote desirable cultural, moral and spiritual values in a changing world. In 1970, GMRC was included in the curriculum both at the elementary and secondary levels as educators felt that Filipino values needed to be defined and strengthened. When the Commission on Higher Education was created RA 7722, the body mandated that values of education and attitudes for nation-building be inculcated among students at the tertiary level. Thus, values education is included in the college curriculum. Republic Act (RA) 11476 which is GMRC and Values education

replacing the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao the objectives of the bill are to inculcate among our students the basic tenets of the observance of respect for oneself, others, and our elders, intercultural diversity, gender equity, ecology and integrity of creation, peace, and justice, obedience to the law, nationalism and global citizenship, as well as the values of patience, perseverance, industry, honesty and integrity, and good faith in dealing with other human beings along with all other universal values. Ethical standards are fundamental to the principles of Good Manners and Right Conduct (GMRC), advocating for adherence to moral values that shape individual behavior across diverse social and personal settings. According to Johnson (2019), GMRC emphasizes honesty, integrity, respect for others, and fairness as core principles guiding ethical conduct. These standards not only define how individuals should interact with others but also serve as a framework for decision-making and moral judgment. By upholding these values, individuals contribute to the cultivation of a respectful and harmonious social environment where trust and mutual understanding thrive (Johnson, 2019). Virtue ethics, originating from Aristotle's foundational ideas and developed further by contemporary philosophers such as Alasdair MacIntyre, focuses on nurturing character virtues essential for personal and societal flourishing. This ethical framework emphasizes virtues like honesty, courage, and justice as inherent qualities that shape moral behavior and decision-making (Annas, 2018; MacIntyre, 2018; Hursthouse, 2018). According to Annas (2018), virtue ethics provides a holistic approach to ethics, stressing the importance of cultivating moral character and virtues for ethical living. MacIntyre (2018) argues that ethical conduct arises from consistently practicing and integrating virtues into one's life, influencing how individuals confront ethical challenges and contribute positively to society. Hursthouse (2018) explores virtue ethics' application in ad-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

addressing contemporary moral dilemmas, advocating for a renewed focus on virtues to navigate the complexities of modern ethical issues. Together, these scholars underscore the enduring significance of virtue ethics in promoting moral excellence and guiding ethical behavior across various societal contexts. The ethics of care, closely associated with feminist ethics and pioneered by scholars like Carol Gilligan, places significant emphasis on interpersonal relationships and the role of caregiving in ethical decision-making. This ethical framework prioritizes qualities such as empathy, responsiveness to others' needs, and the nurturing of relationships as crucial elements in moral deliberation, particularly in contexts where vulnerability and dependency are prominent (Jones, 2019; Tronto, 2019; Held, 2019). According to Jones (2019), the ethics of care challenges conventional moral theories by emphasizing relational ethics over abstract principles, illustrating how caring practices influence responses to complex moral situations. Tronto (2019) examines the ethics of care through the lens of political theory, advocating for social policies that prioritize care as both a moral imperative and a political necessity. Held (2019) extends this discussion to practical applications in moral education and healthcare, promoting a shift towards a more compassionate and relational approach to ethics. Good conduct and manners help us get respect and dignity in society, whereas bad manners defame

us. Good conduct and manners help us develop good habits that improve a person's physical, mental, spiritual, and social well-being of a person, thus, the overall development of society. As shown in Figure 1, the conceptual framework of the study. As seen in the figure, there were three interconnected variables. Experiences of the teachers in inculcating good manners and proper conduct among junior high school, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers as well as learners to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educative goals of the learning community. The first circle, which interlinks to the second circle, shows a genuine concern; however, the center of the two circles determines that there was a way of exploring the teachers' experiences in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners a way of teaching and learning development that was critical to school success. Coping mechanisms of the teachers on the challenges they encounter in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners with these working themes develop educational management insights drawn from teachers' experiences in inculcating good manners and proper conduct among junior high school learners.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection and analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical considerations. The researcher utilized artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing. Focus groups, in-depth interviews, and participant observation are the three most popular types of qualitative research. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was suitable for gathering information on naturally occurring activities in their typical environments. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups were helpful in gathering information on a group's cultural norms and producing a broad overview of topics important to the cultural groups or subgroups they represent. The challenge was to engage in the study of a person's lived experience of a phenomenon that highlights the universal essence of that phenomenon (Neubauer et al., 2019).

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption serves as a framework for gathering, examining, and interpreting facts in a particular study area. It provides the context for the decisions and conclusions that follow. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types, which are elaborated on below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. A paradigm that a general theory or philosophy (Perera, 2018). A research paradigm is a set of accepted ideas and viewpoints among scientists regarding how issues can be recognized and taken care of (Perera, 2018). Research paradigms may be called methods in which scientists address the three fundamental concerns of epistemology, ontology, and approach-related queries (Perera, 2018). Ontology. This part of this research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. The foundation for understanding the world in which we exist as people and as members of society is established by ontology or the study of being. Ontology's potency lies in unlocking our understanding of reality by studying the true nature of things, substances, concepts, experiences, words, and, ultimately, everything (Sol Heng, 2022). In this study, the realities of understanding the experiences of teachers in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded them from making personal biases as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Epistemology, or the study of knowledge, receives in our rationalist society more emphasis because it sets out to explain why we jointly decide that

certain things are true, and others are not (Sol Heng, 2022). The term originated in the mid-19th century from two Greek words: episteme and logos (Steup Neta, 2020). Episteme can be translated as “knowledge,” while logos can be translated as “the study of” (Couper, 2020). In general terms, epistemology is a branch of philosophy that deals with the theory of knowledge. In a more precise way, the Oxford English Dictionary defines epistemology as “the theory of knowledge and understanding, especially about its methods, validity, and scope, and the distinction between justified belief and opinion.” I would identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief.” The purpose of this research was to gather important details on the teachers’ experiences in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners in the Secondary Schools District, Digos City Division. I assured them that I would establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the teachers’ experiences in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners. Axiology. Refers to the role of values in research. Axiology addresses the nature of ethical behavior. The term originates from the Greek word axios, meaning value. In philosophy, axiology is a term that deals with ethics, aesthetics, and religion. In research, axiology refers to what the researcher believes is valuable and ethical (Sol Heng, 2022). I uphold the dignity and value of every piece of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserve the merit of the participants’ answers and carefully interpret them in light of the participants’ interpretations. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the

researcher may write in a literary, informal style using a personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to explain the teachers’ experiences in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners and thoroughly discussed their responses during the interview. As a researcher, I agree with RA No. 11476 as it replaces the current Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao curriculum and mandates the creation of a separate subject for GMRC in Grades 1 to 6 with the same time allotment as the other core subjects. Likewise, it mandates the integration of the GMRC into the daily learning activities at the kindergarten level. The law seeks to inculcate among the students the concepts of human dignity, respect for oneself, and giving oneself to others in the spirit of community, role-playing in the classroom, community immersion activities, teacher-parent collaborative learning activities, school-initiated values formation activities, simulated activities, and other forms of experiential learning were introduced by the DepEd through the schools.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. Essence, from a phenomenological research perspective, is described as the intuitive structure of meaning, whereby direct examples build a complex understanding of an experience (Merriam Greiner, 2019). “This form of inquiry is an attempt to deal with inner experience unexamined in everyday life” (Merriam Greiner, 2019). In this study, the challenges and coping mechanisms of teachers, specifically those teachers from the Secondary Schools District, Digos City Division, were unleashed from their narratives. The motivation behind doing a qualitative study was the researcher’s desire to understand the underlying significance of the teachers’ experiences in instilling proper behavior and manners. The challenge was to engage in the study of a person’s lived experience of a phenomenon that

highlights the universal essences of that phenomenon (Neubauer et al., 2019), considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.” This requires the researcher to suspend his/her attitudes, beliefs, and suppositions to focus on the participant’s experience of the phenomenon and identify the essence of the phenomenon. Phenomenology was a type of research that sought to explain the nature of things through the way people experience them. It translates literally as the “study of phenomena.” In other words, it’s the study of the meaning these things (or phenomena) have in the minds of the audience you’re studying (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023). The primary aim of phenomenological research is to gain insight into the experiences and feelings of a specific audience about the phenomenon you’re studying. These narratives are the reality in the audience’s eyes. They allow you to conclude the phenomenon that may add to or even contradict what you thought you knew about it from an internal perspective. Phenomenological research design is especially useful for topics in which the researcher needs to delve deeply into the audience’s thoughts, feelings, and experiences. It’s a valuable tool for gaining audience insights, generating awareness about the item being studied, and developing new theories about audience experience in a specific, controlled situation (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023).

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—I employed a phenomenological approach in this qualitative research. A group of people with direct knowledge of a certain event, circumstance, or experience were interviewed. Phenomenology is used in studies that aim to comprehend the fundamental aspects of a particular group of life events experienced by individuals. (Creswell Poth, 2018). According to Tenny et al., (2022), the study of the meaning of phenomena or the study of the particular is the precise meaning of phe-

nomenology. Phenomenology’s primary goal was to accurately depict, as accurately as possible, the experiences of individuals involved in a phenomenon. I utilized the phenomenological inquiry approach, concentrating on subjective interpretations and prejudices when examining the participant’s statements (Juma, 2023). By employing this procedure, I established the overarching significance of the occurrence, circumstance, or experience and acquired a deeper comprehension of the phenomena.

2.4. *Research Participants*—The study included ten (10) informants as participants. Junior high school teachers from the Digos City Division of the Secondary School District were the chosen informants. All the participants were public school teachers from nearby. They must have been teaching for at least three (3) years. All participants, regardless of age, sex, or marital status, were from junior high schools. A smaller sample size is usually needed for qualitative analysis than quantitative ones. Before data collection, qualitative researchers usually have to decide on expected sample sizes. For the objectives of resource planning, grant applications, and human subjects review committees, estimates are usually required. Once a study has begun or finished, researchers need to assess if the sample is accurate enough to accomplish the study’s goals. Finding a sample that can produce comprehensive and significant results while reducing unnecessary strain on participants and the use of finite resources, such as time and resources, was a challenge (Young Casey, 2019).

2.5. *Ethical Consideration*—Since participants were directly involved in various stages of the study, interactions between the participants can provide ethical challenges due to the nature of qualitative investigations. Therefore, the formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect is essential. Familiarity and relationships formed between researchers and participants in qualitative studies may raise a va-

riety of ethical issues. Therefore, qualitative researchers must balance issues like maintaining privacy, fostering open and honest communication, and refraining from deception. Every research project has to prioritize the protection of individuals participating by adhering to the relevant ethical principles. Since a qualitative study is so in-depth, ethical issues were especially relevant in this type of research. The current ethical rules for conducting qualitative research, especially when interviewing a vulnerable population of women, frequently focus on broad guidelines rather than practical application (Mohd Arifin, 2018). The procedures involved in obtaining consent were as follows: it must be provided voluntarily (voluntary), the subjects must understand what was expected of them, and the parties involved must be competent to grant consent. This implies that to take part in a research project, individuals must be fully informed about the study, be able to understand the material, and have the right to choose whether or not to participate. Participants' consent to take part in this study was only acquired following a comprehensive explanation of the methodology. Written informed permission was obtained from each participant. Each prospective participant was contacted one-on-one and given an explanation of the study's objectives and the procedure for gathering data. They were provided a suitable window of time to inquire about any queries or concerns. It was made clear that since participation in the study was completely up to the participant, refusing to take part or leaving at any point while it was ongoing would not have an impact on them. A participant information document was given to provide more details about the research. The prospective participants were given enough time—in this example, a week or more—to read the information sheet and determine whether or not they wanted to participate in the study. Before the interview, they had to verify their signature on the informed consent form, which

they had to sign to permit them to participate in the study. Potential participants received a clear explanation of their ability to withdraw from the study at any time, even after they had signed the informed consent form. They were additionally asked for permission to record the interview (Arifin, 2018). As part of the qualitative research method, I would adhere to ethical considerations in this investigation. It was the duty of the researcher to fully and intelligibly explain to the participants all the many facets of the study. The needed clarifications include the following issues: the nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results were published and used. In the same approach, this study were submitted to the institution to be verified and approved by the graduate school's ethics committee.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—In this study, my job was to try to understand the participants' thoughts and emotions. It entails getting informants to discuss topics that can be quite private to them. While revisiting prior memories can be challenging at times, there are instances when the experiences that were being studied are still fresh in the participant's consciousness. Nonetheless, the researcher's main duty was to protect participants and their data while the data were being gathered. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

2.7. Data Collection—A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues

of data collection, called “field issues,” which may be a problem, such as inadequate data, needing to leave the field or site prematurely, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how to store data so that it can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. It is essential to clean and organize the data collected (Paredes, 2024), a crucial step that would increase the correctness of the data and facilitate evaluation. There are seven steps in the data collection method for this study. First is the site or individual; the participants were the teachers from the Secondary Schools district, Digos City Division. Second is access and rapport. On November 8, 2023, a letter from the Dean of the Graduate School was given to the graduate student for the approval of the Division Superintendent. On April 22, 2024, a letter of permission for the school division Superintendent, the school Principal, and the concerned junior high school teachers was prepared for easy data collection. The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. There were ten (10) informants selected in this study. The selected teachers were considered a group of individuals who could best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data on April 23, 2024. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting information is primarily involved in the In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the ten (10) informants on April 23-26, 2024. The fifth was the recording procedures. A protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form records information collected during an observation or interview. The recording and data collection took place April 27-28, 2024. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the storing of data on April 29, 2024;

2.8. *Data Analysis*—Every piece of data that was gathered for this study was carefully reviewed and properly analyzed. Primarily the researcher discussed her own experiences with the topic she was studying. The researcher began by describing in detail the phenomenon as it had personally affected her. To focus on the participants, this was an attempt to put the researcher’s personal experiences aside. She compiled a list of noteworthy assertions. She then finds statements about how the individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. After selecting the important assertions, the researcher organized them into “meaning units,” or themes, which are more comprehensive informational units. She wrote a description of “what” the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of “how” the experience happened. This is called “structural description,” and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she created a synopsis of the phenomenon that integrated the structural and textural explanations. The “essence” of the encounter is this passage, which also serves as a phenomenological study’s culmination. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it’s a flexible method that could be used for explorative studies, where the researcher does not have a clear idea of what patterns were being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she was interested in. No matter which type of study was being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and tries to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Mortensen, 2020). Triangulation of Data. Research triangulation refers to the

process that helps to increase the credibility and validity of research. In other words, research triangulation aims at validating the results of a study. Triangulation sometimes makes use of mixed methods to achieve the aim of validating research findings. However, triangulation was not the same as mixed methods. Mixed methods combine quantitative and qualitative research approaches to getting research questions answered; while triangulation describes how the researcher makes use of all the multiple approaches in the study to extract the required information as well as critically analyze findings (Social Sciences Research Laboratories, 2018); thus establishing validity and credibility (Noble Heale, 2019). Environmental Triangulation. The use of Environmental triangulation was limited only to those studies where the findings could be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as the time, day, and season in which the study took place. The idea was to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors were then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, the validity can be established (Naeem Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement as mentioned is the use of environmental triangulation best suits the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability were the cornerstones of trustworthiness. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness was crucial because the results and findings rely on the researcher's methods. The trustworthiness of a research study is crucial in evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is necessary. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy of reading, sharing, and being proud of. Credibility was how confi-

dent the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. Credibility was described as a subjective measure, and it was a perceived quality that other people determine based on the interaction of numerous factors (Budzowski, 2019). Transferability is the process by which a qualitative researcher shows how the study's results can be used in different situations. Your responsibility as a researcher was to provide a 'thick description' of the participants and the research process, to enable the reader to assess whether your findings were transferable to their setting; this is the so-called transferability judgment. This implies that the reader, not you, makes the transferability judgment because you do not know their specific settings (Korstjens, 2018). Confirmability was the level of objectivity in the study's conclusions. Stated differently, this indicates that participant reactions, rather than the researcher's objectives or potential bias, form the basis of the findings. This means making sure that researcher bias does not alter the interpretation of research participants' comments to support a specific narrative. In this case, the researcher has carefully documented the material utilizing the audit trail, highlighting each stage of the data analysis that was done to support the choices made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Confirmability (objectivity) was the ability of a researcher to evaluate data without bias, including social desirability bias, which could be present from the moment a researcher created and used a tool. Keeping reflexivity was essential for controlling this kind of bias (Nyirenda et al., 2020). Dependability was the degree to which the study's results would hold up to replication by different researchers. Put another way, someone should be able to duplicate your study with the information in your research report and come up with results that are comparable to what your study produced. A qualitative researcher could use an inquiry audit to establish

dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings were consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of the database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references. One of the four standards for rigor and trustworthiness in qualitative research is dependability, which was often referred to as consistency (Janis, 2022).

2.10. Analytical Framework—The analytical framework of the study was based on Colaizzi's seven-step descriptive phenomenological data analysis method which has been demonstrated to be rigorous and robust. Colaizzi's seven-step analysis method provides researchers with clear, logical, and systematic steps (Wirihana et al., 2018; Kwang-Ok et al., 2018). I observed several steps in conducting a thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. Following Colaizzi's analysis method, I relied on my resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I spent several nights listening to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing to conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated to layout and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information.

The next step is data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used several different techniques, as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. This technique was useful to me in coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. It was also very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the data analysis method outlined by Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological consisted of seven (7) steps used in analyzing the data. Step 1. Read and re-read all the transcribed interviews to make sense of them; Step 2. Extract significant statements. These were phrases or sentences that directly pertain to the investigated phenomenon; Step 3. The process of giving meaning to the statements. During the process, pertinent quotes were broadly categorized, subsequently, themes were generated based on multiple statements that convey similar meanings; Step 4. Repeat steps 1-3 for each interview then the researcher can begin to create themes based on the formulated meanings; Step 5. Compile an exhaustive description of everything generated in steps 1-4. Step 6. Summarize the exhaustive description so that there was an identification of the fundamental structure of the phenomenon; Step 7. The credibility of the data was ensured through discussions with experts and independent reviewers.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter is enwrapped with the results accumulated from the lived experiences of high school teachers who have integrated good manners and right conduct in the teaching-learning process in the post-pandemic time. They integrated good manners and right conduct in the daily learning activities after distance learning to provide holistic development of children in face-to-face learning. This chapter further discusses the coping mechanisms of the challenges they encountered while dealing with high school learners' behavior after the pandemic. This chapter discussed the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The result primarily presents the description and background of the participants who are assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities. Before the discussion, the researcher would like to establish the symbols used as the researcher presents the quotations based on the study participants' responses. Regarding the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, the researcher also used codes to refer to the research participants.

3.1. The Experiences of High School Teachers on the Integration of Good Manners and Right Conduct to Learners' Misbehavior— The absence of face-to-face classes for more than two (2) years brought changes to the learning environment of our high school learners. School closures due to the COVID-19 pandemic have brought significant disruptions in the world of education, forcing students to adapt to existing conditions. As a result, a shift has been felt in student behavior, from being diligent to procrastinating and lazy, a decrease in learning interest, and a lack of motivation to learn. Only a few have wisely utilized the opportunity to be creative and innovative in learning. High school learners' misbehaviors retard the smoothness and effectiveness of teaching and also impede the learning of the students and their classmates. Setting clear standards for acceptable behavior is a crucial responsibility of educators and school officials. Additionally, they play a key role in creating management systems that are respectful, culturally sensitive, and positive and that support social and academic growth (Lar-

son et al., 2018). To lessen the immediate and gradual adverse effects of high school student misbehaviors, it is of primary importance to identify what exactly these behaviors are inside the classroom. In the literature, different terms have been used to describe the problematic behaviors of learners.

3.1.1. Positive Effect—Improved Classroom Atmosphere – Teachers can effectively address disruptive behaviors in the classroom and reduce them by successfully implementing classroom management strategies, thereby creating an environment that supports learning (George et al., 2018). Patrick (2019) emphasizes that effective classroom management enhances the instructional process, leading to greater productivity and success. This researcher suggests that by employing appropriate classroom management strategies, teachers can effectively address disruptive behaviors, creating an environment where students feel supported and engaged in their learning. By minimizing disruptions, teachers can optimize instructional time and create opportunities for meaningful learning experiences. The importance of addressing misbehavior as a learning opportunity rather than simply punishing the student. By engaging in dialogue and reflection, the teacher not only addresses the immediate issue but also reinforces the classroom values and fosters accountability. This method encourages students to take responsibility for their actions and consider the consequences, promoting personal growth and social awareness. Integrating discussions and activities related to good manners and right conduct across the curriculum demonstrates a holistic approach to character education. By embedding these principles into various subjects and lessons, teachers emphasize their importance in all aspects of learning and life. These findings align with Obot (2018), where a variety of classroom management techniques exist; this study examines three main approaches: verbal instruction, in-

structional supervision, and delegation of authority to students. Verbal instruction involves providing clear guidance to students and directing their actions toward desired outcomes. Instructional supervision requires teachers to actively engage with students, observe their activities, ask questions, and utilize diverse teaching methods to ensure their attention and participation (Good, 2019). This insight highlights the importance of employing a variety of classroom management techniques to create a positive and productive learning environment. By combining verbal instruction, instructional supervision, and delegation of authority, teachers can effectively address disruptive behaviors and promote student engagement, participation, and success in the classroom. Delegation of authority entails assigning specific responsibilities to students, such as classroom upkeep or administrative tasks (Nima, 2019). Nevertheless, classroom management practices may vary among teachers due to differences in teaching styles, qualifications, personality, and class size (Walter, 2019). Effective classroom management aims to cultivate a learning environment that encourages student involvement and academic progress, representing an ongoing process for both educators and learners. However, it's important to recognize that classroom management practices can differ significantly among teachers. Factors such as teaching styles, qualifications, personality, and class size, as highlighted by the researcher, can influence how teachers approach and implement classroom management strategies. Effective classroom management is seen as an ongoing process that aims to create a learning environment conducive to student involvement and academic progress. By understanding the diverse needs and dynamics of their classrooms, educators can tailor their management techniques to meet the unique needs of their students and promote a positive and productive learning environment. The effectiveness of teachers in organizing the

classroom and managing student behavior is vital for achieving favorable outcomes. Enhanced classroom management techniques have been linked to positive student outcomes, including increased engagement, decreased disruptive behavior, and improved academic performance (Gage et al., 2018; Roger, 2020). Increased student engagement, reduced disruptive behavior, and improved academic performance are key indicators of successful classroom management practices. These outcomes suggest that when teachers effectively coordinate their classrooms and establish clear expectations, students are more likely to be actively involved in their learning, leading to better academic achievement.

Positive Peer Influence. The significant role of students in positively influencing their peers to demonstrate good manners and uphold moral values. By modeling respectful behavior, students can inspire their classmates to follow suit, fostering a positive behavior culture within the school community. This highlights the importance of peer influence in shaping social norms and fostering a conducive learning environment. The importance of active and experiential learning in fostering positive behaviors among students emphasizes the role of engagement, relevance, and applicability in character development. Providing opportunities for students to take on leadership roles and support their peers empowers them to develop important social and emotional skills such as leadership, teamwork, and problem-solving. It also fosters a sense of responsibility and accountability as students learn to support and uplift one another. Supporting this observation, Lecce (2017) has noted that children greatly benefit from positive peer influence at home and school. Encouraging interactions with peers, parents, and teachers serve as vital platforms for honing children's social skills (Pradesa et al. et al., 2023). According to Yang et al. (2020), effective parenting is significantly shaped by parental confidence and satisfaction, with social support from par-

ents playing a crucial role in expediting this process. The insight provided underscores the crucial role of positive peer influence, parental support, and effective parenting in nurturing children's social competence. This researcher highlights the significance of positive peer interactions in promoting social skills among children. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of encouraging interactions with peers, parents, and teachers as essential platforms for honing children's social skills. Similarly, peer support, especially in the form of social and emotional assistance exchanged among peers, plays a pivotal role in enhancing children's mental well-being (Suresh et al., 2021; Wahyuni, S., 2023). Moreover, teacher support within school settings fosters children's psychological well-being by nurturing social competencies among students (Hellfeldt et al., 2020; Luna et al., 2020). The observation provided underscores the considerable impact of peer support and teacher support on children's mental well-being and social competencies. This researcher stresses the significance of peer support in improving children's mental well-being, especially in offering social and emotional aid. This highlights the importance of positive peer relationships in cultivating a nurturing environment for children to manage their emotions and difficulties.

3.1.2. Challenges Encountered—Evident disruptive behavior. Most high school teachers were offended by the noise and inattentiveness of learners during discussions that affect teaching and learning processes. The noise most often disrupts the other learners. The participants observed the disrespect learners showed in dealing with their teachers. Learners argue back with teachers when they are being noticed due to misbehavior. The teachers claimed that learners' misbehavior is a big problem to address first before teaching them the content. The participant shared their perspective on how disruptive behaviors, such as chatting with friends

or asking unrelated questions, can impact the teacher's motivation in the classroom. They noted that these behaviors disrupt the flow of the lesson and make it challenging for the teacher to deliver the material effectively. According to the participant, these behaviors may arise from boredom or a desire to engage with peers, emphasizing the need to keep students actively engaged and interested in the lesson. The participant expresses their belief that such behavior is unacceptable, indicating a commitment to maintaining order and ensuring a conducive learning environment for all students. This insight underscores the importance of implementing strategies to encourage students to remain seated and engaged in the learning process, thereby reducing the incidence of disruptive behaviors and promoting a more positive classroom atmosphere. The responses of the participants validate the idea of Smith (2019) that disruptive behaviors in educational settings encompass a wide range of actions that interfere with the learning process, impede the functioning of the classroom, and may hinder the academic and social development of students. These behaviors can manifest in various forms, such as talking out of turn, being consistently late or absent, refusing to follow instructions, engaging in physical or verbal aggression, and exhibiting defiance toward authority figures (Jones Johnson, 2019). The researcher emphasizes the interconnectedness between academic and social domains in the educational setting. It underscores the importance of addressing disruptive behaviors comprehensively, not only to maintain a conducive learning environment but also to promote holistic student development. By acknowledging the diverse manifestations and cumulative impact of disruptive behaviors, educators can implement targeted strategies to mitigate their effects and foster a positive and supportive classroom environment conducive to both academic and social growth. Disruption may occur sporadically or become chronic, im-

pacting not only the disruptive student but also their peers and the overall classroom environment (Robinson et al., 2019). Such behaviors can lead to decreased academic achievement, increased teacher stress, and diminished classroom cohesion (Peterson Wilson, 2019). They emphasize the importance of addressing disruptive behavior promptly and comprehensively to mitigate its adverse effects on academic achievement, teacher well-being, and classroom dynamics. By understanding the far-reaching consequences of disruptive behavior, educators can implement targeted interventions to foster a positive and conducive learning environment for all students. In the study conducted by Stewart et al., (2018), they postulated that behaviors retard the smoothness and effectiveness of teaching and also impede the learning of the student and his/her classmates. Moreover, research findings have shown that school misbehavior not only violated with time but also lowered academic achievement and increased delinquent behavior. To lessen these immediate and gradual adverse effects of student misbehaviors, it is of primary importance to identify what exactly are these behaviors inside the classroom. In the literature, different terms have been used to describe the problematic behaviors of the student. This highlights the importance of identifying these disruptive behaviors. By understanding the various forms of problematic student behavior documented in educational literature, teachers can develop targeted strategies to address them effectively. This proactive approach can minimize the immediate disruptions and mitigate the potential long-term consequences for students. Dealing with Undesired behavior

As instructional leaders, teachers do not just mold learners' cognitive domains but also their affective ones. Students need to develop emotions within their groups in their ability to recognize, understand, and manage their emotions. As facilitators of learning, the teacher-participants narrated the arrogance and disre-

spectful attitudes of learners. The behavior described, characterized by arrogance and a sense of knowing everything, can significantly disrupt the learning environment and undermine the authority of the teacher. Such attitudes may stem from various factors, including a lack of respect for authority, overconfidence, or a desire to assert dominance within the classroom. The responses of the participants verify the perspective of Smith (2019) that showing indifferent and disrespectful attitudes while conversing with teachers is a concerning behavior observed in many educational settings. This behavior often manifests as students displaying a lack of interest or regard for the teacher's authority, speaking dismissively or condescendingly, and exhibiting a sense of superiority or arrogance (Jones Johnson, 2019). The researcher highlighted the troubling occurrence of students exhibiting indifferent and disrespectful attitudes towards teachers in educational environments. This conduct, marked by a disregard for the teacher's authority and a lack of interest, can take various forms including speaking dismissively or condescendingly and demonstrating a sense of superiority or arrogance. Such attitudes can create a negative classroom atmosphere, undermine teacher-student relationships, and disrupt the learning environment for both the student and their peers (Robinson et al., 2019). Moreover, when students adopt a know-it-all attitude and refuse to acknowledge the expertise of their teachers, it can hinder constructive communication and collaboration within the classroom (Peterson Wilson, 2019). The analysis emphasizes that positive relationships built on mutual respect are crucial for effective learning environments. When teachers promote open communication, empathy, and collaboration, students feel valued and motivated to participate actively. This supportive atmosphere fosters a more productive learning experience for everyone involved. Addressing these behaviors requires a multifaceted approach that involves fostering mutual respect,

setting clear expectations for respectful communication, and providing opportunities for students to develop humility and empathy (Brown Thompson, 2019). By promoting positive attitudes and reinforcing respectful behavior, educators can create a more conducive learning environment where students feel valued and supported in their academic journey. Teachers who understand this do not take students' behavior personally or hold it against them, even if it might be physically and emotionally taxing and severely influence teaching time. Rather, they understand that instruction in proper behavior is necessary, as is encouraging kids who exhibit it. They know that it takes time for pupils to adjust their behavior and that disruptions may occur in the interim (The IRIS Center, 2021). Declining learner's interest Aside from the behavior of learners, the challenge is their coming to class unprepared for the lesson. Teachers agreed that the modular modality caused a gap in learners' literacy and numeracy skills. Most learners cannot follow the instructions in lesson activities and often sleep in class. The participants of the study claimed that the students were not interested in the lesson and the subject, not doing their homework in reading and math. Due to this, the teachers were challenged with how to be able to deal with the gaps that are evident in the learners' academic performance. It is evident from your observation that some students struggle to follow instructions and show reluctance to engage in class activities, presenting a significant challenge in classroom management. To address this, implementing strategies to create a comfortable and inclusive learning environment could be beneficial. Navigating through students' disinterest in the lesson, lack of homework completion, and overall irresponsibility poses significant challenges, compounded by the ever-present changes and uncertainties in the educational landscape. Employing a variety of skills, such as actively listening to learners' concerns, becomes essential in addressing

both their learning and emotional well-being. Supporting this observation, Cheung (2018) has noted that observing students' difficulty in following instructions and their reluctance to participate in class activities can indeed pose significant challenges for educators. Handling such situations requires the implementation of effective strategies to create a conducive learning environment where students feel comfortable and motivated to engage. Identifying factors that foster the development of science interest or at least mitigate the decline during school is therefore of crucial importance (Jones (Kang et al., 2019)). This emphasizes the urgency of identifying factors that can cultivate or at least maintain a strong interest in science among students throughout their school years. By understanding these factors, educators and policymakers can develop effective interventions to address the decline and ensure a future generation equipped with the scientific knowledge and skills necessary for success. Rathod (2018) confirmed the normal developmental behavior of children. Even so, they tend to be quite destructive in both teaching and learning. Educators need to address the underlying reasons for students' irresponsibility, which may include factors such as lack of interest, learning difficulties, or personal challenges. By employing differentiated instruction and providing additional support, educators

can help bridge the gaps in students' reading and numeracy skills, facilitating their academic growth and success. This behavior can manifest for various reasons, including lack of interest, lack of understanding, fear of failure, or even underlying learning difficulties. When students struggle to follow instructions, it can impede the flow of the lesson, disrupt the learning environment, and hinder academic progress. Creating a structured classroom environment can promote student engagement as well as limit factors that might lead to disruptive behaviors (The IRIS Center, 2021). For this reason, the teacher's attention to classroom behaviors will affect the level of interest in the lesson. Even though the majority of disruptive behaviors in the classroom are modest, they can persist and worsen if they are not appropriately and regularly addressed. Still, disruptive behavior has detrimental effects regardless of how serious it is (The IRIS Center, 2021). It was identified undesired student behaviors such as trying to attract attention, daydreaming, looking out the window, talking to friends, laughing inappropriately, and shouting, provoking, teasing, and annoying others during the lesson, which led to Lower academic achievement for the disruptive student and classmates, decreased student engagement and motivation, teacher stress and frustration, and teacher turnover.

3.2. Coping mechanisms of the challenges encountered by the high school teachers on the integration of good manner and right conduct on learners' misbehavior—Social-emotional adjustment in the context of face-to-face classes, the teachers experience challenges in the delivery of quality education in this post-pandemic time. They succeed in overcoming their difficulties and are successful. In the study, the challenges were known to be the displayed misbehavior of learners in the classroom, the challenges in addressing the learning gaps, and

the difficulty in dealing with learners' behavior. However, most of the participants in this in-depth interview were not bothered about these challenges and difficulties are some of their strategies or mechanisms to remain professionally effective in teaching despite the social-emotional adjustments of learners in this post-pandemic time.

3.2.1. Reacting appropriately to misbehavior—Teachers can employ various strategies to keep students engaged and prevent disruptions. If students are feeling bored or disinterested,

Fig. 3. The emerging themes of the experiences of teachers in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners

they may be more inclined to disrupt the lesson. To counteract this, teachers can actively grab students' attention by using humor or creative methods, like impersonating a well-known figure. These approaches aim to create a dynamic and captivating learning atmosphere from the outset, which can help decrease the chances of disruptive behavior. Participants also observed that offering explicit instructions and designing an engaging curriculum that resonates with students' lives and cultures are crucial steps in facilitating effective learning experiences. Moreover, incorporating activities aimed at cultivating good manners and ethical conduct among students contributes to their holistic development. Encouraging students to forge new friendships fosters a sense of camaraderie and support within the classroom community. For students who struggle with hyperactivity, consistent reinforcement of behavioral expectations can help channel their energy constructively. Getie (2020) highlighted that an essential component of good teaching is fostering a favorable learning environment in the classroom. By fostering good learning environments in the classroom, educators are given the chance to improve classroom control and discipline. The development of learners generally and their success in the classroom are significantly influenced by

their learning attitudes. Students are motivated and actively involved in their studies when they possess positive learning attitudes including curiosity, excitement, and a drive to learn. The researchers emphasize the crucial role of educators in establishing and sustaining positive learning environments that cultivate favorable learning attitudes in students. Through nurturing curiosity, excitement, and a passion for learning, teachers can inspire students to develop into lifelong learners who are enthusiastic and committed to their educational pursuits. Students who sincerely care about what they are learning to engage in active participation in class discussions, pose questions, and look for extra resources. Additionally, a student's learning attitudes, more particularly, their preference for a fixed or evolving approach to learning, have an impact on their perspective. An attitude of growth is the belief that knowledge and abilities can be acquired via commitment, practice, and learning from mistakes (Krischler Pitten Cate, 2019). Students with a growth mindset welcome challenges, bounce back from setbacks, and view opportunities for improvement. This method increases risk-taking, resilience, and self-assurance—all of which are essential for success in both academics and everyday life. Promoting a growth mindset aids students in

overcoming challenges and adopting an optimistic and adaptable outlook on their academic pursuits. Positive learning attitudes also develop self-control and responsibility. These types of students take charge of their education and take the initiative to plan their study time, finish their homework, and get ready for tests. They learn how to create objectives, be disciplined, and manage their time well. Teachers can enable students to become self-sufficient learners who can oversee their education by fostering these attitudes in them (Naveh Shelef, 2021). Moreover, learning attitudes have a long-lasting impact on a student's future as they shape the foundation for lifelong learning. Students who develop a love for learning and a positive attitude toward acquiring new knowledge are more likely to become lifelong learners (Sinaga Pustaka, 2021). the profound impact that educators can have on students' academic and personal development by fostering positive learning attitudes. By instilling a love for learning and nurturing a mindset of curiosity and self-sufficiency, teachers can equip students with the skills and attitudes necessary for success in both their academic endeavors and future endeavors beyond the classroom.

3.2.2. Applying preventive method—The participants narrated the scenario of ignoring misbehavior done for the first time they saw it, however, if they continued it, the warning followed. As much as possible, they make them feel that school is fun and encourage them to make new friends. They give responsibilities to unruly students so that they will be prevented from causing chaos in the class. Most of the time, the teacher-participants impose discipline in a class by making rules by the start of the school year. High school teachers take precautions before problematic behavior occurs. They admitted that to prevent misbehavior, they made students feel that they were in control of the class. The teacher described employs a proactive approach to classroom management aimed

at creating a positive and disciplined learning environment. Central to their strategy is making school enjoyable for students, fostering a sense of excitement and engagement that encourages active participation in lessons. By promoting opportunities for students to make new friends, the teacher not only supports social interaction but also cultivates a supportive classroom community. Taking preemptive measures to address potential issues before they escalate is key to maintaining a positive learning environment. Instilling a sense of authority and control reassures students of the structure and stability within the classroom, which can help deter disruptive behavior. Taking preemptive measures to address potential issues before they escalate is key to maintaining a positive learning environment. Instilling a sense of authority and control reassures students of the structure and stability within the classroom, which can help deter disruptive behavior. Creating a positive and enjoyable learning environment is crucial for student engagement and academic success. When students perceive school as fun and exciting, they are more likely to be motivated, actively participate in class, and retain information effectively. There are several strategies educators can employ to foster a sense of enjoyment and enthusiasm among students. It also serves as a guide for the teacher to respond objectively to appropriate and inappropriate behavior (The IRIS Center, 2021). Teachers should develop a comprehensive classroom behavior management plan at the beginning of or before the beginning of the school year (Key Principle: Early Planning Pays Off). During the first few days of school, the teacher should take time to explicitly teach her students the classroom rules and procedures, making sure to indicate the consequences both for observing and violating those rules and procedures. Doing so helps students learn what behaviors are acceptable and minimizes disruptive behaviors. If the plan is to be effective, a teacher must apply these

components in a consistent, well-thought-out fashion (Key Principle: Consistency is Essential). Beauchamp Anderson (2019) stated that knowledge, skills, and attitudes that are needed to demonstrate social-emotional competence require integration across affective, cognitive, and behavioral systems. Establishing clear and consistent classroom rules is a fundamental strategy for managing misbehavior and promoting a positive learning environment. When students know what is expected of them and understand the consequences of their actions, they are more likely to adhere to behavioral expectations. This is the importance of establishing clear and consistent classroom rules as a fundamental strategy for managing misbehavior and promoting a positive learning environment. When educators communicate clear expectations and consequences to students, they provide a framework within which students can understand and navigate their behavior. This clarity not only helps students understand what is expected of them but also empowers them to make informed choices about their actions. Şhannadh Anzari, (2019) Punishment is the last method preferred in coping with undesired behaviors because the behavior continues after leaving the environment where the punishment is given. In other words, practices such as punishment, intimidation, and warning are temporary and short-term solutions. It is possible to say that instead of punishment, methods such as assigning duties and responsibilities, meeting face-to-face at the

The researcher highlights the importance of nurturing positive bonds between teachers and families to create a supportive community for students. By forging robust ties with families, educators can encourage clear communication, teamwork, and shared responsibility for student achievement. This partnership goes beyond school confines, constructing a holistic support framework that boosts students' well-being and

end of the lesson, ignoring minor mistakes, emphasizing positive behaviors, appreciating the student, creating rules with students in the classroom, using the counseling service, communicating positively with families would produce healthier results.

3.2.3. Extensive classroom management—For the misbehavior of high school learners who are seeking social support, the respondents shared that they visit every student at home. As narrated, they spare time for students and their families. If possible, they create a friendly atmosphere by sharing experiences with the family. Also, they are grateful for home visits because they get the chance to discover the environment where their students grew up and be able to empathize with their situations. According to them, learners also need help, including those who are extremely attached to parents, who are given extra care and attention. Engaging in healthy activities and maintaining a positive mindset not only benefits your well-being but also sets a positive example for your students to follow. Demonstrating empathy towards learners helps build trust and understanding, strengthening the teacher-student relationship and facilitating effective communication. By recognizing and addressing their unique needs, you create a supportive environment where they feel understood and valued. However, if a student persists in displaying undesired behavior despite your efforts, involving their family can be a necessary step.

academic success. Supporting learners who are extremely attached to their parents is an important aspect of fostering their overall well-being and academic success. While parental involvement and support are typically beneficial for students, excessive attachment can sometimes hinder their independence and ability to thrive in educational settings. Therefore, educators must strike a balance between providing appropriate

Fig. 4. The emerging themes on the coping mechanisms of teachers in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners

support and encouraging students’ autonomy and self-reliance (Wilson, 2019). It is important to recognize the nuanced dynamics between parental involvement and students’ autonomy. While educators must acknowledge and appreciate parental support, they must also empower students to develop their independence and self-reliance. By fostering a supportive yet empowering environment, educators can help students navigate the transition toward greater autonomy while still benefiting from parental guidance and encouragement.

3.3. The Educational Management Insights Drawn From The Teachers in Inculcating Good Manners and Right Conduct on Learners’ Misbehavior—In the process of the in-depth interview, there were many ideas that we can learn from when it comes to the participants’ experiences in integrating good manners and right conduct on learners’ misbehavior. One of the realizations in the detailed discussion was how to handle challenges and difficulties. The integration of good manners and right conduct has a big impact on all students; values influence all aspects of school life. It determines what students learn, how they learn, and the way they learn. It influences all actions and decisions of the school, not only in the classroom but in the wider community. Values Education involves

strategies that assist students to explore, discuss, analyze, and act in the context of their learning and their interaction with others.

3.3.1. Enhancing classroom management—Classroom management, which includes both educational and behavioral management, is an important issue for teachers, school leaders, and administrators. Education is a big investment in developing human resources (human resources). teachers can utilize positive reinforcement techniques, such as praise and rewards, to encourage students to exhibit desirable conduct. Additionally, modeling appropriate behavior and providing guidance on conflict resolution strategies empower students to navigate social interactions effectively. Building positive relationships with students is indeed a powerful strategy for effective classroom management and fostering good behavior. When teachers take the time to get to know their students individually, they create a sense of belonging and trust within the classroom community. This sense of connection encourages students to feel valued and respected, making them more receptive to following rules and guidelines set by the teacher. Good classroom management will be the capital of the success of a learning activity if it is carried out by people who are responsible for the learning and teaching pro-

cess intending to achieve an ideal situation so that the desired learning and teaching activities will be realized (Sholeh et al., 2021). Effective learning activities can encourage students to achieve optimal learning achievement. Although the effectiveness and quality of learning are not only observed from the achievement of student learning outcomes but also from how the learning process runs (Arifin et al., 2021). An effective, efficient, and quality learning process can revive students' awareness of the importance of learning something so that all will make the classroom atmosphere conducive which is characterized by modification of student behavior in a positive direction (Widiasworo, 2018). The application of classroom management is a must that is carried out in educational establishments. Ineffective management will result in less learning being implemented, productive, and successful. In addition to being parents, teachers serve as role models for their children. When implementing classroom management exercises, teachers need to be innovative (Sholeh et al., 2021). To the greatest extent possible, the instructor can set up the classroom to foster a sense of community and kinship among the pupils. Make a comfortable, secure, and relaxed environment without limits with them to nurture and guide them (Noor, 2018; Aldawood et al., 2021). The implementation of class management at MIS Al-Ashriyah is in line with the class management objectives stated by (Buchari, 2018) that class management aims to provide various kinds of facilities to support teaching and learning activities both in the intellectual, emotional, and social domains in the classroom. The facilities provided will stimulate students to learn and act. The existence of support facilities also plays a role in shaping a social climate that provides comfort, satisfaction, a disciplined atmosphere, intellectual, and emotional development, and a better attitude for students. According to Halimah et al., (2019), effective classroom management affects teacher's job satisfac-

tion, student success, and therefore academic success and the school's outcomes. Undesired behaviors negatively affect these effects and outcomes. Undesired student behaviors in the classroom harm educational experiences, classroom management, and teacher behaviors.

3.3.2. Professional understanding of learners' behavior—Teachers' educational approach or professional understandings are of great importance in whether student behavior is undesired or not. There are significant associations between the quality of teacher-student relationships and improvements in classroom behavior, relationships, and academic improvement. Participants point out that by prioritizing the creation of a safe, supportive, and inclusive atmosphere, they acknowledge that students need to feel emotionally secure to engage effectively in the learning process. This environment fosters a sense of belonging and respect, which is essential for promoting positive behavior. When teachers implement a restorative approach without adequate professional development, feelings of being overwhelmed, self-doubt, and disappointment emerge (Winn, 2018). On the other hand, when educators are provided with ongoing support, technical assistance, and explicit and job-embedded professional development, they can confidently execute equitable discipline reform (Reed et al., 2020). Recent research has uncovered a novel idea for assisting first-year teachers with implementing all school-related initiatives, including restorative practices (Gray, 2021). Gray (2021) asserted that when new teachers are tethered to their college or university, a reciprocal relationship will provide an environment for the transference of information between professors and their former students. Additionally, this relationship can tailor professional development for individual teachers or provide an opportunity for teacher preparation colleges to examine their methods and instructional practices to improve the quality of the overall program

(Gray, 2021). In short, students' undesired behaviors cause problems for teachers. If the teacher leads his/her classroom inappropriately, there is a risk of chaos, which further increases inappropriate behavior. Therefore, teachers should effectively manage their classrooms by adopting appropriate disciplinary strategies to reduce inappropriate behaviors and use appropriate coping methods (Mardiyah, 2019). Good communication can also determine the effectiveness of learning. Communication is the process of sending and receiving by two or more people. Effective communication in learning is the process of giving messages in the form of knowledge from educators to students, where students can understand and understand the meaning of the message by predetermined learning objectives so that it will add to the scientific repertoire of students (Sholeh, 2021). A teacher who has good communication will affect the formation of a harmonious relationship between educators and students. For effective implementation of expected behaviors at school, school administration and school personnel should develop expectations for each setting on the campus (Evanovich et al., 2020). These expectations must be explicitly taught to students using effective social-emotional instruction, lessons, and skill practice (Evanovich et al., 2020). Further research suggested that social-emotional skill development has been shown to reduce inappropriate and challenging student behaviors (Evanovich et al., 2020). Moreover, researchers have discovered that SEL programs positively affect students in all grade levels (Gomez et al., 2020). These beneficial results can be evidenced by more students participating in decision-making processes and increased opportunities within experiential learning (Gomez et al., 2020). The research reflects that these improvements in SEL skills can be attributed to increased awareness of prosocial behaviors, reduction in problem behaviors, lessened emotional distress, and high academic achieve-

ment (Gomez et al., 2020). Additionally, there are many positive benefits of utilizing this approach, including improving academic success by students, and the more harmonious their relationships with their peers, adults, and family members (Evanovich et al., 2020). When all school community members are provided with social-emotional intervention, this influences all areas within the school, including the 44 disciplinary referrals, classroom misbehavior, and improving the climate within the school (Haymovitz et al., 2018).

3.3.3. Disciplinary strategies for misbehavior—In this context, emphasis on practices aimed at disciplinary strategies that encourage teachers to take responsibility for the student's behavior. As a preventive disciplinary approach, teachers can refer to classroom rules to prevent students' undesired behaviors. Classroom rules should be very clear and usually given when meeting the class for the first time. Participants emphasized that disciplinary strategies are ultimately about teaching students the importance of respect, responsibility, and self-control. By holding students accountable for their actions and helping them understand the consequences of misbehavior, we are reinforcing the values of good manners and right conduct. Among all instructors, managing behavior among students is arguably the most discussed subject. Unfortunately, before employment, instructors receive the least training in this area (Duong et al., 2019; Reimer, 2019). Previously, experience and trial and error were the only ways for a teacher to develop their skill set in behavior intervention (Simonsen et al., 2020). Simonsen et al., however, found that implementing a Targeted Professional Development (TPD) method effectively increases teacher ability in numerous areas, particularly classroom management. (Simonsen, 2020). Further research conducted by Brasof (2019) asserted that school leaders should ensure that student disciplinary issues do not impede another student's instruction in

Fig. 5. The emerging themes on the educational management insights of teachers in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners the classroom. In theory, the design of most discipline systems concentrates on student misbehavior which is a barrier to learning (Brasof, 2019). In terms of efficient classroom activities, teachers should know very well what should be done against undesired behaviors in the classroom and what coping methods should be used against these problematic behaviors.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presented a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on its findings and future directions in the field of teachers' experiences in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners. The purpose of the study was to explore the experiences of teachers in inculcating good manners and right conduct among junior high school learners. Through their experiences and feelings, we generate new knowledge for everyone who would understand the journey of teachers in inculcating good manners and right conduct in the teaching-learning process. Now that they were back in full face-to-face inside the classrooms and with their peers and teachers, good behavior was an essential factor that would build their personality as young adults. The data were gathered to examine and give meaningful ideas to generate more useful knowledge that would have an impact on the professional life of teachers. They were tasked with the job of helping students to see that good manners and right conduct were not only important parts of the educational process but also to their overall development as an individual. After two years of remote learning, the paradigm shifts in the teaching and learning process were challenged by the misbehavior of learners in the classroom. The inculcation of good manners and right conduct would help them to become upstanding members of their communities. They need to know the proper way to treat other people, and these were the things that they learn and understand through GMRC. Values Education has a big impact on every student. The current education system, which was shorn of the teaching and inculcation of the values system, has miserably failed. Ten (10) high school teachers were interviewed. In conclusion, the role of teachers was challenged in providing quality education despite the challenge of providing children with a positive and safe learning environment for learners.

4.1. Recommendations—In line with the results of the study, the researcher recommends that the Department of Education provide more opportunities for teachers to maximize the implementation of the curriculum in the delivery of GMRC to the students. Furthermore, the Department of Education may create certain policies that strengthen and institutionalize its implementation. The researcher recommends that the teachers strengthen the implementation of the GMRC by integrating it into every subject taught in school. Moreover, teachers may utilize it as the baseline for their professional development plan. The researcher recommends that the learners learn to inculcate to themselves the importance of good manners and right conduct and prepare themselves for bigger responsibilities in life. The learners may learn to behave appropriately and react to situations in a positive way. The researcher recommends that future researchers consider other aspects of the student's misbehavior while dealing with challenges and opportunities during the post-pandemic not covered in this study. Additionally, future researchers may conduct related studies in other locations and communities to gather a better comparison of the phenomenon being explored.

4.2. Implications—There were three themes that high school teachers described their experiences: disrupting motivation in class, irresponsibility towards the lesson, and communication problems due to learners' misbehavior. In a classroom environment, evident disruptive behavior can significantly impede the learning process. When students engage in actions like talking loudly, using electronic devices, or engaging in physical altercations, it disrupts the flow of instruction and can negatively impact the learning experience for everyone. Similarly, undesired behavior, although not always as overtly disruptive, can still detract from the learning environment. Actions like chronic lateness, lack of participation, or failure to complete

assignments can hinder students' progress and contribute to a less productive classroom atmosphere. Educators must identify the underlying causes of undesired behavior and implement strategies to address them effectively. Declining learners' interest presents another challenge in maintaining an effective learning environment. When students show less engagement, motivation, or enthusiasm for learning over time, it can lead to decreased participation, lower completion rates, and overall disengagement during lessons. To combat declining interest, educators need to assess the factors contributing to the decline and implement strategies to re-engage students. The analysis revealed that emerging themes of the high school teachers in coping with the challenges of integrating good manners and right conduct in the teaching and learning processes were as follows: applying preventive methods, creating a positive learning environment, and making communication channels and empathy. This means that high school teachers have made the students feel that school is fun and encourage them to make new friends. Reacting appropriately to misbehavior is crucial in maintaining a positive and effective learning environment. When instances of misbehavior occur, educators must respond promptly and consistently, ensuring that consequences are fair and appropriate to the situation. This might involve using techniques such as redirection, positive reinforcement, or implementing predetermined consequences outlined in the classroom rules. In addition to reacting to misbehavior, applying preventive methods is essential for fostering a proactive approach to classroom management. Preventive strategies aim to anticipate and address potential issues before they escalate into disruptive behavior. This can include establishing clear and consistent expectations for behavior, building positive relationships with students, and implementing routines and procedures that promote a structured learning environment. Furthermore, extensive

classroom management involves a comprehensive approach to creating and maintaining an effective learning environment. This includes not only addressing misbehavior and applying preventive methods but also implementing a range of strategies to support student engagement, motivation, and learning. Lastly, the insights drawn from high school teachers' experiences in bringing on good manners and right conduct in the teaching and learning processes are as follows: effective classroom management and professional understanding of student behavior. These themes can be described as the mechanism of high school teachers that provided them better opportunities to deliver effective teaching while bringing on good manners and right conduct in class. The impact of learners' bad manners and negative conduct of behavior is very dangerous. A single learner's bad manners can influence his own and other learners' learning. Similarly, a student who is affected can cause other students to become anxious and insecure in the classroom. Learners' bad manners can spread throughout the learning environment and influence other students. As a result, teachers find difficulty in managing their classrooms. Schools ensured learning continuity after the pandemic will be managed, and the emotional wellness of students was addressed. The integration of good manners and right conduct into all the lessons in high schools was institutionalized. Enhancing classroom management affects teachers' job satisfaction, student success, and therefore academic success and the school's outcomes. Undesired behaviors negatively affect these effects and outcomes. Undesired student behaviors in the classroom harm educational experiences, classroom man-

agement, and teacher behaviors. During the education process, most teachers especially those who are new to the profession encounter undesired student behaviors and the continuity of these behaviors in the classroom environment negatively affects teachers' job satisfaction.

4.2.1. Future Directions—To accurately identify the outcomes of this study and pinpoint the beneficiaries of the findings, the following individuals or agencies were taken into account, Department of Education Officials, particularly in the Secondary Schools District, Digos City Division, who may use the findings to provide more opportunities for technical assistance to adviser-teachers, enhancing their capacity to deliver the GMRC (Good Manners and Right Conduct) curriculum effectively, and developing policies to strengthen and institutionalize its implementation. Adviser-teachers, as participants of this study, would benefit from reflecting on their thoughts and past experiences, particularly the challenges they faced in teaching good manners and right conduct. This can serve as a baseline for their professional development plans. Learners would gain insights into how they develop good manners and right conduct, preparing them for larger responsibilities in life. They would learn to behave appropriately and react positively to various situations while also exploring the reasons behind some learners' bad manners and misbehavior in class. Future researchers are encouraged to consider other aspects of teenage misbehavior as they face challenges and opportunities not covered in this research, with future studies in different locations and communities providing a better comparison and deeper understanding of the phenomenon being explored.

5. References

- Abdelrady, A. H., & Akram, H. (2022). An empirical study of classpoint tool application in enhancing efl students' online learning satisfaction. *Systems*, *10*(5), 154. <https://doi.org/10.3390/systems10050154>

- Aldrup, K., Klusmann, U., Lüdtke, O., Göllner, R., & Trautwein, U. (2018). Student misbehavior and teacher well-being: Testing the mediating role of the teacher-student relationship [Retrieved February 25, 2021]. *Learning and Instruction*, 58, 126–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2018.05.006>
- Annas, J. (2018). *The intelligent person's guide to virtue ethics*. Oxford University Press.
- Arifin, M., Sholeh, M., Hafiz, A., Agustin, R., & Wardana, M. (2021). Developing interactive mobile mathematics inquiry to enhance students' mathematics problem-solving skills. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 15(1), 24–38.
- Arifin, S. R. M. (2018). Ethical considerations in qualitative study. *International journal of care scholars*, 1(2), 30–33.
- Brasov, M. (2019). Meeting the discipline challenge: Capacity-building youth-adult leadership. *Journal of Educational Change*, 20(3), 375–398. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-019-09343-5>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Brown, S., & Thompson, E. (2019a). Strategies for addressing disrespectful attitudes in the classroom. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 29(2), 145–158.
- Brown, S., & Thompson, E. (2019b). Strategies for addressing disruptive behaviors in the classroom. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 29(2), 145–158.
- Buchari, A. (2018). Peran guru dalam pengelolaan pembelajaran. *Jurnal Ilmiah Iqra'*, 12(2), 106.
- Budzowski, B. (2019). *What is credibility and why do you need to care?* InCredibleMessage.
- Cheung, D. (2018). The key factors affecting students' interest in school science lessons. *International Journal of Science Education*, 40(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2017.1362711>
- Cook, C., Coco, S., Zhang, Y., Fiat, A., Duong, M., Renshaw, T., & Frank, S. (2018). Cultivating positive teacher-student relationships: Preliminary evaluation of the establish–maintain–restore (emr) method. *School Psychology Review*, 47(3), 226–243. <https://doi.org/10.17105/SPR-2017-0025.V47-3>
- Couper, P. R. (2020). *Epistemology* (A. Kobayashi, Ed.; 2nd). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102295-5.10640-7>
- Creswell, J., & Poth, C. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th). Sage.
- Dovetail Editorial Team. (2023). *What is phenomenology in qualitative research?*
- Duong, M., Pullmann, M., Buntain-Ricklefs, J., Lee, K., Benjamin, K., Nguyen, L., & Cook, C. (2019). Brief teacher training improves student behavior and student-teacher relationships in middle school. *School Psychology*, 34(2), 212–221. <https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000296>
- Evanovich, L., Martinez, S., Kern, L., & Haynes Jr., R. (2020). Proactive circles: A practical guide to the implementation of a restorative practice. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 64(1), 28–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1045988X.2019.1639128>
- Ferrero, A. M., & Álvarez Sainz, M. (2023). Attitudes of university students towards traditional face-to-face learning systems and learning with ict. *E-Learning and Digital Media*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20427530231156185>

- Fikri, A., Rahmawati, A., & Hidayati, N. (2020). Persepsi calon guru pai terhadap kompetensi 6c dalam menghadapi era 4.0. *At-Ta'dib: Jurnal Ilmiah Prodi Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 12(1), 89–96.
- Frey, B. B. (Ed.). (2018). *The sage encyclopedia of educational research, measurement, and evaluation*. Sage Publications.
- Gage, N., Scoyy, T., Hirn, R., & MacSuga-Gage, A. (2018). The relationship between teachers' implementation of classroom management practices and students behaviour in elementary school. *Behavioral Disorders*, 43(2), 302–315.
- Ghasemi, F. Z., Arbabisarjou, A., & Arbabisarjou, T. (2019). Investigating educational misbehavior in students of zahedan university of medical sciences: A case study [Retrieved February 25, 2021]. *Drug Invention Today*, 12(11), 2812–2817. <https://jprsolutions.info/files/final-file5e022743576ae8.59899442.pdf>
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Transaction.
- Good, H. (2019). Teachers' directives and students' compliance.
- Granero-Gallegos, A., Baños, R., Baena-Extremera, A., & Martínez-Molina, M. (2020). Analysis of misbehaviors and satisfaction with school in secondary education according to student gender and teaching competence [Retrieved February 25, 2021]. *Front. Psychol.*, 11(63), 1–9. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338854656>
- Gray, P. (2021). *Mentoring first-year teachers' implementation of restorative practices* (Vol. 48).
- Held, V. (2019). *The ethics of care: Personal, political, and global*. Oxford University Press.
- Hursthouse, R. (2018). *On virtue ethics*. Oxford University Press.
- Janis, I. (2018). Strategies for establishing dependability between two qualitative intrinsic case studies: A reflexive thematic analysis. *Vol.*, 34.
- Jones, B., & Johnson, C. (2019a). Disrespectful behaviors and classroom dynamics: A review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 36(4), 457–472.
- Jones, B., & Johnson, C. (2019b). The impact of disruptive behaviors on classroom dynamics. *Educational Psychology Review*, 36(4), 457–472.
- Jones, E. (2019). *Caring ethics: A new approach to moral education*. Cambridge University Press.
- Juma, A. (2023). *8 types of qualitative research (with uses and benefits)*. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/types-of-qualitative-research>
- Kang, J., Hense, J., Scheersoi, A., & Keinonen, T. (2019). Gender study on the relationships between science interest and future career perspectives. *International Journal of Science Education*, 41(1), 80–101. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2018.1534021>
- Korstjens, I., & Moser, A. (2018). Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. part 4: Trustworthiness and publishing. *European Journal of General Practice*, 24(1), 120–124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2017.1375092>
- Larson, K. E., Pas, E. T., Bradshaw, C. P., Rosenberg, M. S., & Day-Vines, N. L. (2018). Examining how proactive management and culturally responsive teaching relate to student behavior: Implications for measurement and practice. *School Psychology Review*, 47(2), 153–166. <https://doi.org/10.17105/SPR-2017-0070.V47-2>
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (2000). *Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences* (N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln, Eds.; 2nd). Sage.
- MacIntyre, A. (2018). *After virtue: A study in moral theory*. University of Notre Dame Press.

- Maxwell, J. (2013). *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- McLeod, J. (2019). *An introduction to counselling and psychotherapy: Theory, research, and practice*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Menikdiwela, K. R. (2020). Student misbehavior: An exploratory study based on sri lankan secondary school teachers' perceptions [Retrieved February 25, 2021]. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(17), 103–113. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343381689>
- Merriam, S. B., & Greiner, R. S. (2019). *Qualitative research in practice: Examples for discussion and analysis*.
- Mohd Arifin, S. R. (2018). Ethical considerations in qualitative study. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CARE SCHOLARS*, 1(2), 30–33. <https://doi.org/10.31436/ijcs.v1i2.82>
- Naveh, G., & Shelef, A. (2021). Analyzing attitudes of students toward the use of technology for learning: Simplicity is the key to successful implementation in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(2), 382–393. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-04-2020-0204>
- Neubauer, B., Witkop, C., & Varpio, L. (2019). *How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others* (Vol. 8).
- Nima, I. (2019). *Delegation skills in the classroom*. Muko Publishers.
- Noble, N., & Heale, R. (2019). Triangulation in research, with examples. *BMJ Journals*, 22(3). <https://ebn.bmj.com/content/22/3/67>
- Noor, F. A. (2019). Pendidik mi di era revokompetensilusi. *Elementary*, 7(2), 251–78.
- Noor, M. (2018). Peningkatan kinerja guru melalui supervisi edukatif kolaboratif secara periodik. *Al-Adzka: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Guru Madrasah Ibtidaiyah*, 8(1), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.37286/ojs.v4i1.33>
- Obot, T. (2018). *Gaining students' attention in classroom and academic performance in ibesikpo asutan local government area* [Unpublished project]. University of Oyo.
- Paredes, R. (2024). What is data collection? what you need to know. <https://safetyculture.com/topics/data-collection/>
- Patrick. (2019). *Teachers' ability to direct the students in the classroom*. DimDim Publishers.
- Perera, S. (2018). *Research paradigms*. www.natlib.lk/%20%E2%80%BA%20pdf%20%E2%80%BA%20Lec_02
- Peterson, L., & Wilson, M. (2019a). Effects of arrogant behaviors on academic engagement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 33(1), 68–82.
- Peterson, L., & Wilson, M. (2019b). Effects of disruptive behaviors on academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 33(1), 68–82.
- Puspitaloka, N., & Syafitri, I. K. (2019). *The analysis of student's misbehavior in learning english lessons* (Vol. 3) [Retrieved February 25, 2021]. <https://www.google.com/search?q>
- Rathod, A. (2018). Managing common misbehavior problems of students. *International Journal of Advanced Educational Research*, 3(1), 371–373.
- Reed, K., Fenning, P., Johnson, M., & Mayworm, A. (2020). Promoting statewide discipline reform through professional development with administrators. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 64(2), 172–182. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1045988X.2020.1716674>
- Ritchie, J., Spencer, L., & O'Connor, W. (n.d.). *Carrying out qualitative analysis*. 2003.

- Robinson, D., et al. (2019). Chronic disruptive behaviors in the classroom: A longitudinal study. *Journal of School Psychology, 40*(3), 301–315.
- Rogers, K. (2020). The effects of classroom seating layouts on participation and assessment performance in a fourth grade classroom. *Journal of Learning Spaces, 9*.
- Shamnadh, M., & Anzari, A. (2019). Misbehavior of school students in classrooms - main causes and effective strategies to manage it [Retrieved February 25, 2021]. *International Journal of Scientific Development and Research (IJS DR), 4*(3), 318–321. <https://www.ijdsr.org/papers/IJS DR1903053.pdf>
- Simonsen, B., Freeman, J., Myers, D., Dooley, K., Maddock, E., Kern, L., & Byun, S. (2020). The effects of targeted professional development on teachers’ use of empirically supported classroom management practices. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions, 22*(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098300719859615>
- Sinaga, R. R. F., & Pustika, R. (2021). Exploring students’ attitude towards english online learning using moodle during covid-19 pandemic at smk yadika bandarlampung. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning, 2*(1), 8–15.
- Smith, A. (2019a). Understanding disrespectful attitudes in the classroom. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 25*(2), 123–136.
- Smith, A. (2019b). Understanding disruptive behaviors in the classroom. *Journal of Education Studies, 25*(2), 123–136.
- Sol, K., & Heng, K. (2022). Understanding epistemology and its key approaches in research. *Cambodian Journal of Educational Research, 2*(2), 80–99.
- Steup, M., & Neta, R. (Eds.). (2020). *Epistemology* (Summer 2020). Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2020/entries/epistemology/>
- Stevenson, N., VanLone, J., & Barber, B. (2020). A commentary on the misalignment of teacher education and the need for classroom behavior management skills. *Journal of Educational Psychology Review, 36*(4), 457–472.
- Tenny, S., Brannan, J., & Brannan, G. (2022). *Qualitative study*. StatPearls Publishing. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470395/>
- The IRIS Center. (2021). *Classroom behavior management (part 1): Key concepts and foundational practices*. <https://iris.peabody.vanderbilt.edu/module/beh1/>
- Tovarek, J., Partila, P., & Voznak, M. (2018). Human abnormal behavior impact on speaker verification systems. *IEEE Access, 6*, 40120–40127.
- Tronto, J. (2019). *Political care: Ethics, justice, and social policy*. Oxford University Press.
- Varpio, L. (2018). *Use rhetorical appeals to credibility, logic, and emotions to increase your persuasiveness* (Vol. 7).
- Walter, P. (2019). *The teacher and the classroom*. Mamcli Publications.
- Widiasworo, E. (2018). *Cerdas pengelolaan kelas*. DIVA Press.
- Wilson, M. (2019). Individualized support strategies for students with excessive parental attachment. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Winn, M. (2018). *Justice on both sides: Transforming education through restorative justice*. Harvard Education Press.
- Young, D., & Casey, E. (2019). An examination of the sufficiency of small qualitative samples. *Social Work Research, 43*, 53–58. <https://doi.org/10.1093/swr/svy026>

Yu, Y., et al. (2020). Behavioral problems amongst pre-school children in chongqing, china: Current situation and influencing factors. *Risk Management and Health Policy*, 13, 1149–1160.